

SEEING TRUST – SMELLING TRUST COMMUNICATING EMOTIONS THROUGH DESIGN IN ARTISTIC PERFUMERY

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ABSTRACT

This paper is about a designed object that communicates the emotion of trust in a perfume-making process. Analyzing the design of the object it raises the issue of how to represent and communicate an emotion visually. This question has previously been discussed in the context of mood boards and other board objects used in design processes. The analysis of the empirical case however reveals that this designed object significantly differs from conventional mood-boards in terms of the designed elements, the degree of elaboration, authorship, changeability and the function in the design process. As a visual concept the designed object communicates a personal interpretation of trust to the different stakeholders in the design process. Yet, the concept cannot simply be de-coded. Instead, the complex design of the emotion involves the user in meaningful sense-making activities. Thus, the case from artistic perfumery shows how the design of new communication objects enables cross-disciplinary design processes for emotion related products.

Keywords: design analysis, emotion, design process, communication, mood board, emotion

INTRODUCTION

Emotions are deeply intertwined with the sense of smell. The sense of smell triggers strong emotions, and olfactory memories can be more evocative and longer-lasting than sight. The direct link between the olfactory receptors and the human limbic system accounts for the smell sense as a strong emotional driver. This is the reason why particularly fine

fragrances appeal to the spectrum of human emotions. However, how can an emotion be translated into a scent? And how can a particular emotion be communicated across the different design professions taking part in a fragrance development process?

This paper tells the unusual story of an extraordinary design process in the emerging field of artistic perfumery. The brand behind the scents is known for the “unconventional concepts behind the highly individual perfume creations” (<http://www.fragrantica.com/designers/Humiecki-%26-Graef.html>). What is special about the brand is that “each scent is inspired by atypical, emotionally evocative, motifs such as madness, melancholy and fury” (<http://www.humieckiandgraef.com/>). In the highly competitive perfumery market each of the eight existing scents is discussed as “a unique artwork in a modern flacon of clear, streamlined design” (<http://www.fragrantica.com/designers/Humiecki-%26-Graef.html>).

This paper analyses the communication design that facilitates the communication between an art director developing the concept of the scent and the perfumers working on the scent. It focuses on the visual concept developed by the art director and used by the other creative professions involved in the process (e.g. perfume-making, packaging design, photography, text editing). Analyzing the visual concept of the eight concept this paper looks at how emotions are communicated through design. The case of the visual concept is discussed in the broader context of objects and communication in design processes. So far, this discussion has mainly dealt

with mood boards as the central device to communicate in design processes. However, this paper shows that there are other effective formats (e.g. visual concepts) to communicate emotions through design.

The paper is part of a larger study on the role of objects in design processes funded by the Swiss Science Foundation. In this context we have been able to closely follow the development of the eighth and ninth perfume. The emotion that provided the inspiration for the perfume was “trust”.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: We start by reviewing the existing literature on the use of mood boards as a communication device in design processes. This section synthesizes the key characteristics of mood boards and their use in design processes. In the following section we describe the research methods used for generating and analyzing the data. Subsequently we present our design analysis of the visual concept that communicates the emotion of “trust” to the other involved creative professions. The paper concludes with a set of consequences derived from this case.

COMMUNICATING IN DESIGN PROCESSES

Since the design methods movement in the 1960s design processes and practices have been discussed as communication processes. Accordingly, the design process leads from the “world of imagination” into the “world of concrete objects” (Aspelund 2006). Objects enable communication and serve other technical and non-technical functions (Crilly, 2010). In particular, mood boards are recognized as central communication devices mediating between different stakeholders in design processes (Eckert and Stacey, 2003).

A mood board has been described as a sketchy collage used in creative presentations to introduce the context of a draft (Godlewsky, 2007). It is created from diverse, mainly abstract material (images, text, textures, scents etc.). The material is arranged on a defined format, freely or defined by a grid. Mood boards are created by one designer or, less frequently, within teams. The design of mood boards

is a well-known part of contemporary design education. Thus, figure 1 illustrates the common understanding of the key characteristics of a mood board within the design profession.

Figure 1. Mood board for a perfume of the brand “Vivienne Westwood” created by a design student (<http://michelledigital.com/missing-moodboards/>)

In particular, mood boards have previously been discussed in the context of product design (Baxter, 1995): In this context the mood board “tries to identify a single expression of values for the product” (Baxter, 1995, p. 222). It is often distinguished from other related concepts. Thus, the mood board differs from the lifestyle board, which communicates the target group and the social values of the design, and the visual theme board, which collects images of products to communicate the mood that the design is intended to create. The lifestyle board can also be classified as a mood board (McDonagh and Stenton, 2005). The style board corresponds with the concept of the visual theme board (Baxter, 1995). Theme boards are described similar to mood boards in the context of fashion industries (Eckert and Stacey, 2003). A theme board communicates “actual forms and features designers plan to use in their new designs” (Eckert and Stacey, 2003). Just like the mood board, it is also used to express a mood “to indicate the context of the designs” (Eckert and Stacey, 2003, p. 534).

With respect to its use in design processes, mood boards fulfill multiple functions in design processes: Designers use mood boards for inspiration (Eckert and Stacey, 2000), to represent the results of a research process (Eckert, 2001), to express a mood, to evoke an emotion or to develop a concept and communicate it to the stakeholders of a design

process (McDonagh and Storer, 2004). Often a mood board serves more than one function in a design process. During the process they are regularly reviewed and updated (McDonagh und Storer, 2004).

Typically, the mood board is used to communicate with the client. In presentations, mood boards impart emotions and moods to the stakeholders. Images are used to show the social and aesthetic context of the design concept: “By referring to sources of inspiration designers can convey concepts very concisely” (Eckert and Stacey, 2000). The mood board communicates the touch and feel of the final product. The visual format can easily communicate across cultural and professional boundaries (McDonagh und Storer, 2004).

Designers are trained to communicate through images. That is why mood boards are preferred to, or used additionally to verbal concepts. By employing tactile, visual and olfactory elements, they communicate beyond the mere verbal boundaries (McDonagh und Storer, 2004). This is particularly relevant when communicating specific emotions that can hardly be captured by words.

Mood boards are generally understandable: each element used on it makes a statement on the design product. They provide an indication of color, appearance, material and emotional charge around the result. However, the interpretation of the mood board is inevitably subjective (McDonagh und Storer, 2004). Consequently, misunderstandings can easily arise. Textual elements are used to concretize the statement of the images (McDonagh und Storer, 2004).

Elements of design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Images · Texts · Typographic elements · Textures · Scents · etc.
Degree of elaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Sketchy · Incomplete
Authorship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Teamwork · Individual
Target users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Designers · Non-designers
Changeability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Updated during design process
Function in design process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Inspiration · Presentation of research results · Developing of a concept · Express a mood · Evoke an emotion · Indicate the context of a design · Communication to the stakeholders · Compensation of different backgrounds

Table 1. Specifications of mood boards

Table 1 summarizes the above literature review on mood boards as a communication device. Accordingly, there has been substantial research on the use and function of mood boards in design processes. However, very little is known about the object itself used as a communication device in a design process. In addition, previous research has almost exclusively looked at field of fashion and textile design. This might be part of the reason why the design of emotions has hardly been discussed.

RESEARCH METHOD

DATA GENERATION

Our data stem from twelve intensive months of an ethnographic study on the entire process of developing a new perfume in the field of artistic perfumery. Eckert and Boujut (2003) argue that an ethnographic approach is particularly well suited for design processes, because it allows the researcher to capture the complex processes in their uniqueness. We followed various objects around “for their meanings are inscribed in their forms, their uses, their

trajectories” (Appadurai 1986, 5). The key object we identified is the visual concept designed by the creative director.

The visual concept was developed in various stages over a period of four weeks. Initially, the art director clarifies the general emotional idea for the new fragrance (in this case the emotion of “trust”). He selects diverse visual material out of magazines, books and other printed matter and bookmarks the pages. Afterwards, he scans the images and modifies them in an image-processing program. The product, a new image, evolves by overlaying and multiplying the visual material. To further clarify the message of the concept, a few lines of text are finally added. The concept is subsequently used in the briefing contacts with the other creative professions involved in the process (e.g. perfume-making, packaging, photography, copywriting).

We collected data by participant observation and – whenever possible – video-taped the practices of the art director and the perfume makers in the design office in Zurich (Switzerland) and in the studio of the perfume-makers in Berlin (Germany) and New York (USA). We taped most of the talk, wrote extensive field notes, took pictures of the objects, the actors, the infrastructure and surroundings (office, laboratory, desk); we also collected various materials and objects (including the visual concept). In addition, we carried out open ‘de-briefing’ interviews in which the actors talked about what they were doing and reflected with us on what we had observed.

In this paper we only report on the visual concept. In terms of data the visual concept is a particularly interesting object of inquiry. On the one hand it is a fully and professionally designed object. There seems to be no limits to the efforts used to finalize the object. On the other hand, the concept is only used within the design process. It is not used for external communication. Given the visual complexity and design quality of the concept a thorough analysis is needed to elaborate the design of the emotion.

DATA ANALYSIS

The objective of the analysis is to understand how the emotion “trust” is visually designed in this process.

Given the nature of the designed object the analysis follows a visual methodology. Building on the approach of contextual analysis (Müller, 2003; Müller, 2008) the concept was initially studied within the context of the design process. This method originates in the three stages of iconography (Panofsky, 1980). In addition, it also takes into account the “sociocultural and –political aspects as well as the various factors influencing the visual process of production and reception” of the object to be analyzed (Müller, 2003). Secondly, we base on interpretative segment analysis (Breckner, 2010). Since the designed object consists of multilayered images a closer analysis of the isolated layers turned out to be particularly effective. Thus, the description, analysis and interpretation of the visual concept reconstruct design-related decisions and, even more important, sets free the emotion communicated to the user. Furthermore, based on the segment analysis this approach identifies the underlying patterns in the selection and usage of the original material.

VISUALIZING AN EMOTION: ANALYSIS OF THE VISUAL CONCEPT ON TRUST

How can the emotion “trust” be communicated through a designed object in a design process? The results of the analysis are presented in several steps. First, we look at each page of the visual concept. Subsequently, the image is separated from the rest of the page and closely analyzed. Each image consists of multiple overlaying layers that will be analyzed in detail. Afterwards the analysis shifts to the image as a whole and the accompanying text is taken into account. Finally, the pages are interpreted as part of the entire visual concept.

THE DOCUMENT

The visual concept consists of four pages: A cover sheet, as well as three pages with an image placed in the middle of the page. It is provided as a digital file in Portable Document Format (PDF).

Each page plays a specific role in the visual concept: The second page after the cover sheet introduces the emotion on a visual level. The following page visually details and concretizes the emotion of “trust” further.

The last page of the visual concept provides specific visual clues about desired olfactory notes.

The concept is numbered as 2010-1 on the cover sheet. Apart from this there is no further information about the author or the geographic origin in the document. This indicates that the document is rather “personal” and designed for a small circle of users. Lacking any additional direction the user is free to approach and work with the document in different ways.

THE LAYOUT

The layout is repeated on the three content pages of the concept: Each page consists of an image and two lines of text in German. The emotion “trust” is repeated and followed by the claim on the three pages: “Trust - the feeling of being in good hands”. The word “trust” is emphasized by upper case type. Additionally, there is a varying caption, which refers to the particular image.

THE COVER SHEET

Figure 2. Visual concept “trust”: cover sheet

The cover sheet defines the layout of the overall concept. It arranges the typographic elements and introduces the selected font. Both appear elegant and classic at the same time. But the different elements are arranged in a modern way. Thus, the layout evokes a sense of contemporariness instead of a historic nostalgia. The classic layout indicates that the

art director intends to create a visual concept on a reliable basis, rather than on a progressive idea.

The frame for the images is positioned in the center of the document format. It is constructed out of two squares. The image will be placed in the inner square without a contour. The outer square has an outline and frames the image. The layout provides no visual information on the emotion, the theme of the concept. It is a neutral template, created on a computer, probably as a master page in conventional layout software. It will be filled with new texts and images for every page. Thus, the art director can reuse the template and it can be recognized and attributed by the stakeholders. That is why the template may also be regarded as a guarantee for a coherent appearance and corporate communication.

THE FIRST PAGE

Figure 3. Visual concept “trust”: first page

The first page of the visual concept after the cover sheet consists of an image and two lines of text. The image is constructed out of two layers. Both layers are multiplied, an effect that can be applied in a common image editing program. The result is a new, autonomous image. Combining several layers enhances the ambiguity and complexity of the image. If you look at the photomontage, it communicates a different message than the original images:

Figure 4. Visual concept "trust": first page, first layer

The lowest layer shows a male couple kissing. Both are naked, indicating a romantic situation or sexual relationship. The grey hair suggests middle-aged or older men. Both seem to be of the same age. They have muscular bodies and appear well groomed. The picture could have been published in a contemporary magazine for the gay community. The image is cropped tense. You see one man's back from rump to head, cropping the face above one eye. The other man holds his head and bows his face to kiss him. You can see from his hairline, via his breast and right upper arm to his elbow. The image might have been cut out off a larger picture. In stylistic terms, it refers to renaissance painting, which is strengthened by the color atmosphere. Warm shades of color dominate the image.

Figure 5. Visual concept "trust": first page, second layer

The upper layer shows a cutout portrait of a young man in semi-profile. He looks into the camera seriously. The image conveys the impression that the young man looks in the eyes of the viewer. The man has a neat, handsome appearance that makes you think of a model taken from a fashion catalogue or magazine. The image is cropped at his hairline, on the right edge just next to his ear and underneath his neck, showing his collar. The image is displayed in black and white, maybe processed by the art director. It leaves the user with the impression of the classic beauty of a statue.

Figure 6. Visual concept "trust": first page, both layers

The superimposition of the two motifs leaves a dreamy impression, almost as if the young man were dreaming of his own future. In fact, the two layers visually interact: It seems as if one of the older men were touching the young man's face with his hand. The arrangement is deliberately designed to communicate a statement: Thinking of trust, there is not only a trust-based relationship between the two old men kissing. In addition, the young man refers to the couple. The hand touching the young man's face seems to symbolize trust.

The communicated image of trust is amplified by the claim below "the feeling of being in good hands". The athletic bodies of the older couple radiate protection and security. The gaze of the young man can be linked to the adjectives in the second line of text "relaxed, impartial, yearning". The art director, when selecting the images might have intended this coincidence. The relationship between the three men allows only for presumptions. Is it the young man's dream of his own future that gives him trust?

THE SECOND PAGE

Figure 7. Visual concept "trust": second page

The second page of the concept visually details the theme further. At first sight the image appears vague, almost abstract. Again some layers seem to be multiplied, but can hardly be differentiated. The order of the layers can only be reconstructed by opening the original file.

Figure 8. Visual concept "trust": second page, first layer

The motif of the first layer is a male head with closed eyes, lying on a cushion. The man seems to be asleep. The body is covered with a duvet. The man has a five-day beard and grey short cut hair. On first sight it could be one of the two kissing men shown on the first page. The image focuses on his head by cropping the image narrow. The man looks quite amicable. The meaning of the image seems to be obvious. The colors of the image are rather pale.

Figure 9. Visual concept "trust": second page, second layer

The second layer shows plantlike forms, which remind the user of treetops when looking up to the sky. The

whole image is blurred. This is the reason why it looks diffuse and confusing. It puts the viewer into a condition similar to intoxication. The colors allude to the changing leaves in the autumn, but they appear artificially amplified. Parts of the image recur within the image. Thus, the image might be copied, transformed and multiplied. The image seems to be modified and retouched. All in all, the layer rather creates an atmosphere instead of communicating a clear visual statement.

Figure 10. Visual concept "trust": second page, both layers

By overlaying both layers, the images mutually influence each other. However, the relation cannot be clearly determined. The interference leaves a rather random and unfocused impression on the viewer. This is particularly obvious when comparing this image with the image on the first page of the visual concept. The sleeping man and the blurred forms associate a dream. The diffuse tension reinforces this impression. But, where is trust?

The text takes up the theme of trust and presents a specific interpretation of the emotion: "experiencing natural closeness without the need to change".

Contextualizing text and image one realizes how the autumn colored leaves correspond with the grey hair of the man. Thus, the second line "without having to change yourself" can be read with reference to the mature age of the man. Zooming into the sleeping

man's face visually conveys an intimacy and close affinity. Looking into the sky there might be a religious connotation in the image. In summary, the design of the second page arises from experience and serenity.

THE THIRD PAGE

Figure 11. Visual concept "trust": third page

The final page of the visual concept concretizes the emotion in olfactory terms. It is meant to suggest certain olfactory notes the art director associates with the emotion of trust.

The image is composed of four multiplied layers. The viewer can easily separate them. The second line of text lists the components shown in the picture in correct order and characterizes them even further: "Laurel, grey hair and the strong elegance of a well-balanced red wine".

Figure 12. Visual concept "trust": third page, first layer

The image on the first layer shows four green leaves of a plant, cutout, cropped and arranged on the left side. One of the four leaves stretches into the center of the picture and draws the attention of the user. Their limb lies outside of the picture. Because the image is not manipulated or reduced in opacity, it can easily be identified as the leaves of a plant. But which plant is it? The text points out "laurel". Here a concrete smell is represented by the image of its carrier.

Figure 13. Visual concept "trust": third page, second layer

On the second layer one recognizes the kissing couple from the first page of the visual concept. But

the person on the left hand is retouched out of the image. Thus, one can associate a narrative across the pages. However, in the context of the third page the image conveys an olfactory idea. In this case, the smell of grey hair, as the text reveals. But the image goes beyond the words: It shows a well-groomed elderly man in an act of love.

Figure 14. Visual concept "trust": third page, third layer

The picture on the third layer shows a still of red fluid poured in a glass from the upper right to the lower left edge of the picture. The image has been cropped. Thus, the bottle is not visible and the glass can hardly be recognized as such. The text reveals that the fluid is red wine. In this case the text goes beyond the visual: "and the strong elegance of a well-balanced red wine".

Figure 15. Visual concept "trust": third page, fourth layer

The fourth layer visually specifies the smell of the red wine. It shows three bottles of wine lined up probably on a shelf. The picture is cropped. Consequently, the label of the bottle in the center can be read to some extent: "Châteauneuf-du-Pape", a wine from a village in southern France of the same name. The design of the label indicates a classical type of wine. It is used to illustrate the second line of text visually. The source of the picture could be a reportage or an advertisement for the wine.

Figure 16. Visual concept "trust": third page, all four layers

In this case the text closely corresponds with the image. The four elements mentioned in the text are figuratively present and can easily be recognized. Only the wine appears two times, poured and symbolized as bottles. The different layers are arranged in one consistent visual image instead of merely stringing together different images. Thus, the image adds value to the text although the arrangement does not provide an overall message. But the layering enhances the curiosity and interest of the user.

The design of the third image encapsulates visual clues to olfactory notes. However, in terms of its olfactory implications the third image does not go beyond alluding to possible olfactory notes. There is no information that could be regarded as a quantifiable input for the perfumer.

THE VISUAL CONCEPT

Looking at the three pages of the visual concept side by side, it can be noticed, that beside the layout, the concept is held together by the methods the art director uses to create his visual interpretations of "trust". His personal style of selecting, cropping and overlaying shapes the users perception of the communicated emotion. At second glance, the color range is similar throughout the images shown in the visual concept.

It appears as the art director visualizes trust by using warm and earthy shades of color. Color affects the perception of an emotion. The art director takes advantage of this fact by determining a color range to specify his interpretation of trust.

Finally, there is no narration in the visual concept. But there is a main idea of trust, which is verbalized as a claim on every page: "the feeling of being in good hands". The art director visualizes this concept by the image of an elderly man, which appears in every picture. This image can be interpreted as a father figure. However in the first picture you see a kissing scene, which suggests the elderly men as homosexuals. So trust is also represented as a lover of a higher age. This is a very personal interpretation of trust, which is far away from general definition.

With the help of the visual concept, the user looks at the emotion through the eyes of the art director. The images specifies the emotion more precisely than text. They communicate his personal interpretation of “trust” beyond the sense of the word.

DISCUSSION

The visual concept resembles the design and use of mood boards described in the literature. In fact, design researchers regularly refer to the familiar concept of mood boards when discussing this case of a visual concept: The concept tries to express and induce a certain emotion. Its goal is to get the perfume maker in the “right mood” and it is also the brief that communicates the basic idea for the perfume-maker. Later in the process, the visual concept is also used as a brief in the interaction with the packaging designer, the copywriter and campaign photographer.

However, the analysis of the visual concept identified a higher degree of elaboration. In addition, the versatility in using images as raw material distinguishes the visual concept from conventional mood boards. In contrast to mood boards, the selected raw material is carefully transformed and becomes an undistinguishable part of a new whole. Thus, working with the designed object the visual sources cannot be recognized as such. The multiplicity of sources also enhances the subconscious and emotional effect on the user.

Moreover, the idiosyncratic use of language that can hardly be translated specifies the message of the image and distinguishes the concept from mood boards.

Thus, the visual concept cannot easily be digested. It is neither trivial nor obvious. Instead, it attracts the user to be deeply involved with exploring the complexity of the emotion “trust”.

The personal style of the art director is an important factor accounting for effectively designing an object capturing an emotion. The design of the object deeply resonates the professional identity and personal experiences of its creator. That might be the reason why the visual concept is not designed in teams.

Consequently, the concept cannot simultaneously appeal to a diversity of audiences. The user must be sensitive to the design style of the art director. That is why the visual concept cannot be applied universally – a major limitation compared to mood boards.

The message communicated by the visual concept is multifaceted and must be interpreted subjectively. The concept consists of “strong images” (Boehm 2008). Like artworks, the images require an intensive interaction between user and object. The visual concept evokes associations that influence the thoughts and actions of the user. It provides a “poetic” definition of the final product. The final product is characterized in atmospheric terms rather than technical features.

While mood boards tend to be objects that are worked with during the design process, the visual concept is completely designed at the beginning of the process. It is not changed afterwards. Yet, it plays an active role along the entire process.

The visual concept is ambivalent in its basic structure and function in the design process. It narrows the scope, but at the same time it inspires the user's imagination. The art director communicates a clear idea of the character of the envisioned product. On the other hand the visual concept is open for interpretation. It triggers inspiration and stimulation.

One would expect that the image expands and the textual elements limit the scope of interpretation (Kress, 2005). But looking at the visual concept and its use, it appears that image and text are related in a more complex way. The interplay between text and image keeps the tension. This idea will be pursued in the conclusion.

Elements of design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Images · Texts · Typographic elements
Degree of elaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Highly elaborated
Authorship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Only individual
Target user	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Co-laborators open to design style
Changeability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Static during design process
Function in design process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Inspiration · Binding concept · Point of reference · Sense-making device · Express a personal mood · Evoke an personal emotion · Communication to the stakeholders · Compensation of different interpretations of an emotion · Narrows the scope of the product

Table 2. Specifications of visual concepts

Table 2 summarizes the specific characteristics of the visual concept. A comparison with table 1 reveals the differences to the conventional mood-board.

CONCLUSION

Emotion cannot easily be evoked by words or images. But images can express a specific emotion more precisely than words. It is widely known that images enable symbolic representation of objects and events without verbal translation. They become accessible to mind and emotion by optical reception and evoke recognition and remembering. Visual communication is perceived as faster, more densely and more directly. In summary, images intensively absorb emotions. This characteristic facilitates the communication between the stakeholders in the design process.

The visual concept does not reveal its emotional content upfront. One can only after reading the word “trust” begin with making sense of the emotion “trust”. The interrelation between image and text plays a significant role when examining the visual concept. Text can shift or expand the message of an image and vice versa. It shifts the perception of the motif and contextualizes the emotion “trust”. To understand the

personal interpretation of trust by the art director, an in-depth involvement of the user is needed. In the visual concept, adding elements of text to the image facilitates this involvement.

However, this cannot be attributed to the typographic design of the text and the layout of the pages, which is constant through all the pages of the visual concept, and rather neutral. The choice of the typeface and the arrangement of the elements add no information to the communication of “trust”. But the layout puts the image and text into context and assesses them: It shows, that the image is more important than the text. This is especially relevant when reading the visual concept. In terms of Kress (2005) we are dealing with a new, extensive form of reading in a visual age. Combining text and image supports semantic openness and encourages the reader to maturity. The user obtains his idea of trust from the art director, but at the same time the visual concept motivates him to interpret the images on his own.

The analysis of this paper challenges the very idea of a general design of emotions. Instead, it underlines the significance of personal experience and involvement triggered by a designed object. In a next step the underlying design rules and practices can be applied to other contexts.

REFERENCES

- Appadurai, A. (1986) Introduction: commodities and the politics of value. A. Appadurai (Ed.) *The social life of things*. Cambridge: University Press, Cambridge.
- Aspelund, K. (2006) *The design process*. New York: Fairchild.
- Baxter, M (1995) *Product design: practical methods for the systematic development of new products* London: Chapman and Hall.
- Boehm, G. (2007) *Wie Bilder Sinn erzeugen: die Macht des Zeigens*. Berlin: Berlin University Press.
- Breckner, R. (2010) *Sozialtheorie des Bildes*. Bielefeld: Transcript-Verlag.
- Crilly, N. (2010) The roles that artefacts play: technical, social and aesthetic functions. *Design Studies*, Vol. 31, Issue 4, 311–344.
- Cross, N. (2007) *Designerly ways of knowing*. Basel: Birkhauser.
- Eckert, C. (2001) The Communication Bottleneck in Knitwear Design: Analysis and Computing Solutions. Computer Supported Cooperative Work. *The Journal of Collaborative Computing*, Vol. 10, Issue 1, 29–74.
- Eckert, C., Boujut, J., (2003) The Role of Objects in Design Co-Operation: Communication through Physical or Virtual Objects. *Computer supported cooperative work*, Vol. 12, 145-151.

- Eckert, C., Stacey, M. (2000) Sources of inspiration: a language of design. *Design Studies*, Vol. 21, Issue 5, 523–538.
- Eckert, C., Stacey, M. (2003) Sources of inspiration in industrial practice: The case of knitwear design. *Journal of Design Research*, Vol. 3.
- Godlewsky, J. (2007) Mood Board. In: M. Erhoff (Ed.), Marshall, T. (Ed.), *Wörterbuch Design: Begriffliche Perspektiven des Design*. Basel: Birkhäuser, 281.
- Kress, G. (2005) Gains and losses: New forms of texts, knowledge, and learning. *Computers and Composition*, Vol. 22, Issue 1, 5–22.
- Lawson, B. (1997) *How designers think: the design process demystified*. 3rd edition. Oxford, Boston: Architectural Press.
- McDonagh, D., Denton, H. (2005) Exploring the degree to which individual students share a common perception of specific mood boards: observations relating to teaching, learning and team-based design. *Design Studies*, Vol. 26, Issue 1, 35–53.
- McDonagh, D., Storer, I. (2004) Mood Boards as a Design Catalyst and Resource: Researching an Under-Researched Area. *The Design Journal*, Vol. 7, Issue 3, 16–31.
- Müller, M. G. (2003) *Grundlagen der visuellen Kommunikation : Theorieansätze und Analysemethoden*. Stuttgart: UVK.
- Müller, M. G. (2008) Visual competence: a new paradigm for studying visuals in the social sciences? *Visual Studies*, Vol. 23, Issue 2, 101-112.
- Panofsky, E. (1980) *Studien zur Ikonologie: humanistische Themen in der Kunst der Renaissance*. Köln: DuMont.